

Integrating Physical Activities with Music for Sustainable and Holistic Development of School Children in Winneba, Ghana

Regina Akuffo Darko

Munkaila Seibu

Henry, Augustine Pufaa Jnr

Yayra Kluboito

Department of Health, Physical Education, Recreation and Sports, University of Education,
Winneba, Ghana.

Johnson Mawuli Edu

Latipher Amma Osei

Department of Theatre Art, University of Education, Winneba, Ghana.

ABSTRACT: This study investigated the effect of integrating music into physical activity on Basic Six pupils' cognitive, affective, and psychomotor development in Winneba, Ghana. A single-group pre-test post-test quasi-experimental design was used, involving 28 pupils (14 males, 14 females) purposively selected from the University Practice School. The intervention consisted of two 60-minute sessions weekly for six weeks, incorporating structured physical activities with popular music. Cognitive and affective domains were assessed using a questionnaire, while psychomotor skills were evaluated through flexibility, cardiovascular endurance, and strength tests conducted at pre-and post-test stages. Findings revealed significant improvements in cognitive ($t(27) = 9.74, p < .001$) and affective ($t(27) = 9.73, p < .001$) domains and aerobic capacity ($t(27) = 6.09, p < .001$) except flexibility which showed no significant change ($t(27) = 0.29, p = .777$). These results suggest that integrating music into physical education enhances the holistic development of learners by fostering their cognitive engagement, emotional well-being, and physical fitness. We recommend that physical education lessons should be taught with music especially in primary schools for the holistic development of children as well as to sustain their interest in regular participation in physical activity for lifelong and healthy living.

Keywords: affective, cognitive, psychomotor, aerobic capacity, flexibility, holistic development, music, physical activity etc.

Introduction and Literature Review

Research Methodology

Data Collection and Analysis

Results

Discussion of Findings

Conclusion

Recommendation

References

1. Introduction and Literature Review

Physical inactivity among children has become a critical global concern with far-reaching implications for the health and well-being of individuals and societies (Bull et al., 2020). The issue of physical inactivity is particularly alarming in Ghana, as evidenced by the fact that about 4.2% of deaths and cases of childhood obesity in the country are attributed to the failure to cultivate the habit of engaging in lifelong physical activity from the formative

stage (Global Observatory for Physical Activity, 2018; Nyawornota et al., 2018).). Hence, the battle against the declining rate of physical activity (PA) among children is not only a health imperative but also a socio-economic challenge, necessitating innovative approaches to encourage sustained participation in physical activities from a young age.

According to Bull et al., (2020) alluding to the World Health Organisation recommendation for physical activity (PA) postulate four hundred and twenty (420) minutes of moderate-to-vigorous PA to be accrued per week by children and adolescents to maintain optimal health. Although Gao, et. al. (2018) study emphasised several beneficial natures of PA, Guthold et al., (2020) quantify the PA levels of children to be low and poor. As a result, researchers must concentrate on how children engage in physical activities by incorporating intervention programmes into physical education lessons to boost their interest in participation in PA. As such, one promising avenue for enhancing children's engagement in physical activities is the integration of music into physical activity due to its numerous benefits.

Music has long been recognized as a powerful motivator and enhancer of human experiences. In the context of physical activity, the beats and rhythms of music offer a unique and enjoyable background that makes PA fun, non-competitive, and sociable for children (Public Health - South West, 2020). This extrinsic motivation which consequently ignites intrinsic motivation in children is crucial for sustaining interest and increasing endurance in physical activities, potentially laying the foundation for a lifelong commitment to a healthy and active lifestyle. Again, a study by Taniguchi et al. (2017) reported that physical activity in the form of organised exercise that follows a rhythmic pattern with music improves muscular strength, enlarges muscle cells and creates neural adaptations that enhance neuromuscular interactions in the human body.

Similarly, Wilson et al (2016) stressed that structured physical activity programmes that sustain participants' interest in long physical activities enhance the stroke volume and myocardial contractility of the heart chambers resulting in greater cardiac mass. However, the acquisition of all these numerous cognitive, affective, psychomotor and health benefits among children does not occur as they age, rather motor skill learning and interventions have been proven to enhance the acquisition of these affective and health-related fitness benefits among children (Lubans et al., 2010; Ericsson, 2011). Thus, a need to incorporate music into primary school PA and PE lessons in Ghana.

The traditional approach to Physical Education (PE) often struggles to capture and sustain the interest of school children, contributing to a lack of enthusiasm for regular physical activities. This lack of engagement poses a serious threat to the holistic development of the children, impacting not only their physical health but also their cognitive, emotional, and social well-being (Lopes et al., 2012). According to Dobrescu et al (2012), effective use of music in PE classes has several benefits such as promoting movement, stimulates the creative imagination, supports the development of motor skills and habits, helps disperse weariness, and increases exposure of feelings and emotions, put students in the mood to participate, produce a pleasant working atmosphere and keeps them engaged in their tasks without exhausting them (Barney & Pleban, 2018, Physical Education, 2019). Tuan (2022) reiterated that popular music integration into PA creates a dynamic practice

environment which helps to keep participants on task and improve physical fitness and physical activity participation. Recognizing the potential of music as a powerful motivator and enhancer of human experiences (Thakare et al 2017; Terry et al 2020; Viola et al 2023), there is a growing interest in exploring its role in encouraging sustained participation in physical activities among school children.

Music-based interventions have been widely experimented with in diverse fields of study in some parts of the globe (Chen et al., 2022; Chair et al., 2021), However, the existing gap in research on the integration of music with PA in the Ghanaian context prompts the need for a comprehensive investigation into the effectiveness of such an approach. The lack of empirical evidence on the impact of combining physical activities with music on the holistic development of school children in Winneba necessitates a focused study to address this significant knowledge gap. Additionally, the urgent call to action stems from the broader consequences of physical inactivity, which extends beyond the immediate health implications to encompass socio-economic burdens associated with increased healthcare costs and decreased productivity. The specific problem this study seeks to address is the need for evidence-based strategies to promote sustainable and holistic development among school children in Winneba, with a particular focus on integrating physical activities with music within the educational context. Hence, the purpose of this study was to investigate the effects of six weeks of integrating physical activities with music intervention on the sustainable and holistic development of school children in Winneba, Ghana.

The model that backed this study was the Socio-ecological model (SEM) of health behaviour (Bronfenbrenner, 1979). The SEM recognizes the role of psychosocial elements in behaviour change, as well as the necessity of dynamic person-environment relationships in explaining the complexity of human existence (McLaren & Hawe, 2005). According to the SEM, individual knowledge and attitudes have less of an impact on health behaviour than the surroundings in which community inhabitants live, play, work, and study. In terms of PA, strong scientific evidence suggests that the existence of physical and social surroundings that support exercise appears to considerably enhance individuals' PA levels (Sallis, et al., 2012). The SEM theory was used in this study to show how the integration of music into the Physical Education environment influences participants' knowledge and behaviour for holistic development and sustainable participation in PA for life.

The study addressed the research questions: what are the effects of integrating physical activities with music on the cognitive abilities of school children? what are the effects of integrating physical activities with music on the affective abilities of school children? and what are the effects of integrating physical activities with music on the psychomotor development of school children? A hypothesis which stated that there is a statistically significant difference in participants' cognitive, affective and psychomotor abilities after six weeks of integration of music with physical activities was tested.

2. Research Methodology

This pilot study adopted a single-group pretest-posttest quasi-experimental design to assess the impact of integrating physical activities with music on the holistic development of

school children. The design was chosen because it allowed the researchers to assess the effects and the extent of the effects on the dependent variables when the independent variable was manipulated over a specific period despite the limitations of the design (Rogers & Revessz, 2019). The study was set in Winneba, Ghana, where the prevalence of physical inactivity among school children poses a significant risk to their holistic development. The University Practice School (North Campus) in Winneba provided the setting for this study. The choice of this location allowed for a focused investigation into the effects of the intervention programme on a specific group of pupils in Basic 6. The class was selected because; it is yet to be exposed to the Common Core Standard-Based PE Curriculum.

A purposive sampling technique was employed to select 28 participants from the basic six class. The participants were made up of 14 males and 14 females with an age range of 10 to 13 years. The study used closed-ended questionnaire items to collect data on participants' cognitive and affective domains. The literature reviewed helped the researchers to identify key cognitive and affective variables, which informed the development of the items on the questionnaire. For the psychomotor domain, sit and reach, beep test and inclined push-up counts were used to test for participants' flexibility, aerobic capacity and strength. All these were done under the supervision of the researchers and the 5 research assistants per the test protocols.

Before data collection, an introduction letter was obtained from the Directorate of Research and Innovative Development (DRID) -University of Education, Winneba (UEW) which was used to seek permission from the Ghana Education Service Effutu Municipality. Permission was also sought from the headmistress of the school after the researchers were granted permission from GES. Informed consent was obtained from both participants and their parents or guardians before the pre-test. A date and time were arranged with the class teacher for the pre-test. The researchers with the help of 5 research assistants administered the questionnaire to the participants to fill out to test for their cognitive and affective domains after the researchers had explained the purpose and the instructions to them. In addition, the participants were taken through pre-test activities of flexibility test (sit and reach), cardiorespiratory endurance test (beep test) and strength test in the upper limbs (inclined push-ups). Participants' privacy and confidentiality were strictly maintained throughout the study.

3. Data Collection and Analysis

A week after the pre-test an intervention programme was administered twice a week (Tuesdays and Thursdays) for eight weeks, with each session lasting for 60 minutes based on the teacher's weekly plan for the term. Aerobic dance was introduced in the first week. In week two, participants were taken through throwing and catching activities in handball with music. In weeks three, four, five, six, seven and eight participants went through activities comprising throwing and catching activities in handball with music, throwing and catching activities in netball with music, bounce passes in handball with music, movement techniques in dance, striking a tossed ball above the head to a partner with music and

cardiorespiratory, flexibility, strength activities and games with music respectively. The post-test was conducted a week after the intervention programme.

Descriptive statistics such as means and standard deviations were used to analyze pre-test and post-test variables within cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains. Research questions one, two and three were analysed with paired sample t-test to determine significant impact of the pretest-posttest results by comparing the differences at a 95% confidence level.

4. Results

The demographic results from Table 1 showed that out of the total of 28 participants, 14 were males (50%) while 14 were females (50%). There were six (21.4%) pupils aged 10 years, seven (25.0%) pupils aged 11 years, 10 (35.7%) were 12 years old and five (17.9%) were 13 years of age.

Table 1: Demographics Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic		N	Percent (%)
Age	10	6	21.4
	11	7	25.0
	12	10	35.7
	13	5	17.9
	Total	28	100
Gender	Male	14	50
	Female	14	50
	Total	28	100

The results as presented in Table 2 indicated that the participants after going through the intervention had significantly higher ($M=30.61$, $SD=3.34$) cognitive domain scores than before the intervention ($M=21.54$, $SD=3.28$), $t(27) = 9.74$, $p < .001$. Additionally, the results established that the participants had a significantly higher ($M=31.25$, $SD=2.86$), affective domain scores after going through the intervention compared to their pretest score ($M=23.86$, $SD=4.96$), $t(27) = 9.73$, $p < .001$.

Table 2: Paired Sample t-test Results for Cognitive and Affective Domains

Domains	Tests	N	M	SD	Df	t-value	p-value
Cognitive	Pre-intervention	28	21.54	3.28	27	9.74	.000
	Post-intervention	28	30.61	3.34	27		
Affective	Pre-intervention	28	23.86	4.96	27	9.73	.000
	Post-intervention	28	31.25	2.86	27		

The results from Table 3 revealed an improvement in participants aerobic capacity at the posttest stage ($M=5.85$, $SD= 1.28$), compared to their pretest score ($M=4.70$, $SD=1.23$), $t(27) = 6.09$, $p < .001$. Participants result for muscular strength also improved ($M=15.93$, $SD=8.46$), compared to their pretest score ($M=11.71$, $SD=6.66$), $t(27) = 3.28$, $p < .003$. However, participants flexibility before ($M = 22.91$, $SD = 6.91$) and after going through the

intervention ($M = 23.19$, $SD = 6.48$), $t(27) = 0.29$, $p = .777$ statistically did not score significantly lower or higher.

Table 3: Paired Sample t-test Results for Psychomotor Domain

Domains	Tests	N	M	SD	Df	t-value	p-value
Aerobic capacity	Pre-intervention	28	4.70	1.23	27	6.09	.000
	Post-intervention	28	5.85	1.28	27		
Muscular endurance	Pre-intervention	28	11.71	6.66	27	3.28	.003
	Post-intervention	28	15.93	8.46	27		
Flexibility	Pre-intervention	28	22.91	6.91	27	0.29	.777
	Post-intervention	28	23.19	6.48	27		

5. Discussion of Findings

The sustenance of interest of children in physical activity from childhood through the adolescent stage to adulthood have a significant impact on a life-long attitude toward participation in physical activity to meet current WHO's recommendations for physical activity participation to decrease sedentary lifestyles and associated diseases that affect national development. The provision of interesting music background during physical education lessons creates a favourable climate shift that enhances and sustained physical activity participation leading to significant increase in learners' cognition, mood and intensity (Barney & Prusak, 2015). Research have indicated cognitive gains of engaging in PA with music (Terry et al 2020) which align with the present study findings where there was a surge in participants' cognitive domain at the posttest stage. Also, Archana and Mukilan, (2016) in their study reported music with PA having soothing effect on the mind. Additionally, the findings from this present study revealed a significant improvement in pupils' affective development which is in tandem with the finding of a study by Bryant (2014) who also established that music with PA help to release pressure, work effectively with friends, improve social life and do away with pains associated with performing a giving task as well as improve classroom behaviour and management during PE lessons (Paul, 2013). This supports Bronfenbrenner's Socio-Ecological Model (1979), highlighting the mesosystem's influence on school and community interactions that promote physical activity and music integration. Similarly, a study by Benham (2014) attributed increased level of enjoyment in PE lessons to the use of music. As asserted by Greco et al (2022) that music incorporated into PA modulate the affective responses of enjoyment in the performer.

The present study also saw a tremendous improvement in participants' psychomotor development of strength which is supported by Terry et al (2020) who in their study opined that music with physical activity helps to improve performance, reduce perceived exertion and improve physiological efficiency. The outcomes from this present study conform to several study findings (Bartolomei, et al 2015; Köse, 2018; Cutrufello, et al 2020; Silva et al., 2021) which also found an increase in upper body strength-endurance while listening to motivational music compared to a no-music condition during bench press performance.

Additionally, the present study also revealed a significant improvement in the participants' aerobic capacity which is in tandem with a study by Schoolyard (2016) who asserted that exercise with music increases endurance capacity tricking participants into

performing intense exercise for longer periods. A study by Reynolds (2015) also revealed that students who went through 5 weeks intervention PA programme with music were significantly engaged in more PA with music compared to those without music. Despite each day intervention starting with stretching and other flexibility activities, participants' flexibility did not improve after the intervention. Contrary to this present finding, a study by Leite et al (2017) after subjecting participants into six months resistance training saw an improvement in their flexibility component. Similarly, Ren et al (2024) found significant improvement in primary school pupils' flexibility after going through different aerobic activities for 16 weeks. Also, Simao et al (2011) investigated the effect of flexibility training alone for 16 weeks on participants' flexibility gain and saw an increase when measured by sit-and-reach test. This contrast may be as a result of methodological difference (age of participants, duration for the intervention and setting) between this present study and previous ones referenced. Correspondingly, high sustenance in PA was also reported by Brewer et al (2016) and Stephenson et al (2022).

6. Conclusion

The study concluded that the provision of interesting and popular background music during physical education lessons increases students' participation in physical activity leading to significant development in learners' cognitive and affective domains. The sustenance of interest of children in physical activity has a significant influence on the development of life-long attitudes toward continuous participation in physical activity to decrease sedentary lifestyles and associated diseases that are detrimental to national development.

7. Recommendation

The study recommends that teachers at primary schools should teach physical education lessons with music for the holistic development of children as well as to sustain their interest in regular participation in physical activity for lifelong healthy living. Physical education curriculum planners are recommended to incorporate music into physical activities in the PE curricula to foster the holistic development of pupils. Additionally, health policymakers should formulate strategies to address the global issue of declining physical activity among children, with a focus on integrating music to enhance engagement and sustainability in regular participation in PA for life.

Credit Author Statement

R.A.D.: Conceptualization, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing

M.S.: Conceptualization, Methodology, Data Curation, Writing - Review & Editing

L.A.O.: Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing

J.M.E.: Data Curation, Writing - Review & Editing

H.A.P.J.: Data Curation, Writing - Review & Editing

Acknowledgement

We thank AIESEP for supporting this paper's completion and presentation at the 2024 AIESEP Conference in Jyvaskyla, Finland. We also appreciate the cooperation and support of the University of Education, Winneba Practice School's Headmistress, the Physical Education Teacher, and all participants who contributed to the success of this project.

8. References

1. Archana, R., & Mukilan, R. (2016). Beneficial effect of preferential music on exercise induced changes in heart rate variability. *Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research* 10(5):CC09–CC11 DOI 10.7860/JCDR/2016/18320.7740.
2. Barney, D. & Pleban, F. (2018). An examination of physical education teachers' perceptions of utilizing contemporary music in the classroom environment: A qualitative approach. *The Physical Educator* 75 (2), 195 – 209. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.18666/TPE-2018-V75-12-7447>
3. Barney, D. & Prusak, K. (2015). Effects of music on physical activity rates of elementary physical education students. *The Physical Educator* 72 (2), 247-263
4. Bartolomei, S., Di Michele, R., & Merni, F. (2015). Effects of self-selected music on maximal bench press strength and strength endurance. *Perceptual and Motor Skills* 120(3):714–721 DOI 10.2466/06.30.PMS.120v19x9.
5. Benham, L. (2014). The effects of music on physical activity rates in junior high physical education students. (Master's dissertation) <https://scholarsachive.byu.edu/etd/4370>.
6. Bronfenbrenner, U. (1979). *The ecology of human development: Experiments by nature and design*. Harvard University Press.
7. Brewer, L., Barney, D., Prusak, K & Pennington, T. (2016). Effects of music on physical activity rates of junior high school physical education students. *The Physical Educator*: 73 (4), 689 – 703. <https://doi.org/10.18666/TPE-2016-V73-14-7024>
8. Bryant, S. (2014). The positive influence of playing music on youth. NAMM Foundation. <https://www.nammfoundation.org/articles/2014-06-09/positive-influence-playing-music-youth#>
9. Bull, F. C., Al-, S. S., Biddle, S., Borodulin, K., Buman, M. P., Cardon, G., Carty, C., Chaput, J.-P., Chastin, S., Chou, R., Dempsey, P. C., Dipietro, L., Ekelund, U., Firth, J., Friedenreich, C. M., Garcia, L., Gichu, M., Jago, R., Katzmarzyk, P. T., Willumsen, J. F. (2020). World Health Organization 2020 guidelines on physical activity and sedentary behaviour. 1451–1462. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2020-102955>
10. Chair, S. Y., Zou, H., & Cao, X. (2021). A systematic review of effects of recorded music listening during exercise on physical activity adherence and health outcomes in patients with coronary heart disease. *Ann. Phys. Rehabil. Med.* 64:101447. doi: 10.1016/j.rehab.2020.09.011
11. Chen, W. G., Iversen, J. R., Kao, M. H., Loui, P., Patel, A. D., Zatorre, R. J., & et al. (2022). Music and brain circuitry: Strategies for strengthening evidence-based research for music based interventions. *J. Neurosci.* 42, 8498–8507. doi: 10.1523/JNEUROSCI.1135-22.2022
12. Cutrufello, P. T., Benson, B. A., & Landram, M. J. (2020). The effect of music on anaerobic exercise performance and muscular endurance. *The Journal of Sports Medicine and Physical Fitness* 60(3):486–492 DOI 10.23736/S0022-4707.19.10228-9
13. Dobrescu, T., Rata, G. & Salgau, S. (2012). Music as a means of optimizing the physical education lesson in pre-university education. *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Science.* 46, 4114 – 4118. <https://10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.06.209>.
14. Ericsson, K. A. (2011). The influence of experience and deliberate practice on the

- development of superior expert performance. In K. A. Ericsson (Ed.), *Development of professional expertise: Toward measurement of expert performance and design of optimal learning environments* (pp. 685-706). Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
15. Gao, Z., Chen, S., Sun, H., Wen, X., & Xiang, P. (2018). Physical Activity in Children's Health and Cognition. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/8542403>
 16. Global Observatory for Physical Activity. (2018). *Global status report on physical activity*. World Health Organization.
 17. Greco, F., Grazioli E., Cosco L. F., Parisi, A, Bertollo M, & Emerenziani G. P. (2022). The effects of music on cardiorespiratory endurance and muscular fitness in recreationally active individuals: A narrative review. *PeerJ* 10:e13332 DOI 10.7717/peerj.1333
 18. Guthold, R., Stevens, G. A., Riley, L. M., & Bull, F. C. (2020). Global trends in insufficient physical activity among adolescents: A pooled analysis of 298 population-based surveys with 1•6 million participants. *The Lancet Child & Adolescent Health*, 4(1), 23-35.
 19. Leite, T. B., Costa, P. B., Leite, R. D., Novaes J. S., Fleck, S. J & Simao, R. (2017). Effects of different number of sets of resistance training on flexibility. *International Journal of Exercise Science* 10(3): 354 – 364.
 20. Lopes, V. P., Stodden, D. F., Bianchi, M. M., Maia, J. A., & Rodrigues, L. P. (2012). Correlation between BMI and motor coordination in children. *Journal of Science and Medicine in Sport*, 15(1), 38-43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsams.2011.07.005>
 21. Lubans, D., Richards, J., Hillman, C., Faulkner, G., Beauchamp, M., Nilsson, M., ... & Biddle, S. (2010). Physical activity for cognitive and mental health in youth: A systematic review of mechanisms. *Pediatrics*, 126(6), 1143-1154.
 22. McLaren, L., & Hawe, P. (2005). Ecological perspectives in health research. *Journal of Epidemiology and Community Health*, 59(7), 631-636. doi: 10.1136/jech.2004.028662
 23. Nyawornota, V.K., Luguterah, A. V, Sofo, S., Aryeetey, R., Badasu, M., Nartey, J., Assasie, E., Donkor, S.K., Douglor, V., Williams, H., & Ocansey R., (2018). Results from Ghana's 2018 Report Card on Physical Activity for Children and Youth. *Journal of Physical Activity and Health*, 15(2), S366-S367 <https://doi.org/10.1123/jpah.2018-0459>.
 24. Köse, B. (2018). Does motivational music influence maximal bench press strength and strength endurance? *Asian Journal of Education and Training* 4(3):197–200 DOI 10.20448/journal.522.2018.43.197.200
 25. Rogers, J., & Reverz, A. (2019). Experimental and quasi-experiment designs. In J. Mckinley & H. rose, *The Routledge Handbook of Research Methods in Applied Linguistics* (pp. 133 – 143). London. England: Routledge.
 26. Paul, R. (2013). The role and value of music in physical education lessons in Maltese primary schools. <https://www.um.edu.mt/library/oar//handle/123456789/8985>
 27. Physical Education (2019). Music for physical education classes. *Advancement courses*. <https://blog.advancementcourses.com/classroom-activities/music-for-physical-education-classes/>
 28. Public Health - South West. (2020). Cool Facts - Hot Feet: dancing to health: a review of the evidence, 2011. Retrieved from <https://www.communitydance.org.uk/DB/resources-3/cool-facts-hot-feet-dancing-to-health-review-of-evidence>.
 29. Ren, Y., Chu, J., Zhang, Z & Luo, B. (2024). Research on the effect of different aerobic activity on physical fitness and executive function in primary school students. *Sci Rep* 14, 7956 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-58009-7>
 30. Reynolds, T. (2015). Effects of music on physical activity rates of middle school physical education students. The graduate faculty, university of Wisconsin-Platteville, USA. <https://minds.wisconsin.edu/bitstream/handle/1793/76720/ReynoldsTaylor.pdf?>
 31. Sallis, J. F., Floyd, M. F., Rodriguez, D. A., & Saelens, B. E. (2012). Role of built environment in physical activity, obesity, and cardiovascular disease. *Circulation*, 125(5), 729-737. doi: 10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.111.089047
 32. Schoolyard (2016). Benefits of music and dance in PE class. *School Specialty*. <https://blog.schoolspecialty.com/benefits-music-dance-pe-class>.
 33. Silva, N. R. D. S., Rizardi, F. G., Fujita, R. A., Villalba, M. M., & Gomes, M. M. (2021).

- Preferred music genre benefits during strength tests: Increased maximal strength and strength-endurance and reduced perceived exertion. *Perceptual and Motor Skills* 128(1):324–337 DOI 10.1177/0031512520945084
34. Simao, R., Lemos A., Salles, B., Leite, T., Oliveira, E., Rhea, V. M. (2011). The influence of strength, flexibility and simultaneous training on flexibility and strength gains. *J Strength Cond Res.* 25 (5): 1333 – 1338
 35. Stephenson, R., Beddoes, Z., Otterson, S. & Rugen, J. (2022). Research based practical applications for utilizing music to increase motivation and physical activity in physical education. *Strategies* 35, 17 – 22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08924562.2021.2000539>.
 36. Taniguchi, T., Shinkoda, K., & Kuno, S. (2017). Effects of music-based exercise on muscle strength and neuromuscular function in older adults. *Journal of Aging and Physical Activity*, 25(3), 419-433. doi: 10.1123/japa.2016-0185
 37. Terry P. C., Karageorghis, C. I., Curan, M. L., Martin, O.V., & Parsons-Smith, R. L. (2020). Effects of music in exercise and sports: A meta-analytic review. *Psychol.Bull.* 146 (2), 91 – 117. Doi:10.1037/bul0000216Terry.
 38. Thakare, H. E., Mehrotra, R., & Singh, A. (2017). Effect of music tempo on exercise performance and heart rate among young adults. *International Journal of Physiology, Pathophysiology and Pharmacology*, 9(2), 35-39. 10.15341/jppp/9/2/68
 39. Tuan, T. M. (2022). The effect of popular music on female students' fitness in physical education courses. *Annals of Applied Sport Science.* 10(1), 1120. <https://dx.doi.org/10.52547/aassjournal.1120>.
 40. Viola, E., Martorana, M., Airoidi, C., Mieni, C., Ceriotti, D., Vito, M. D., Ambrosi, D. D. & Faggiano, F. (2023). The role of music in promoting health and wellbeing: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *European Journal of Public Health* 33(4):738-745. Doi:10.1093/eurpub/ckad063
 41. Wilson, M.G., Ellison, G.M., & Cable, N.T. (2016). Basic science behind the cardiovascular benefits of exercise. *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 50(2), 93–99. doi: 10.1136/bjsports-2015-095201